

Ideal Photon

In the vast realm of physics, photons stand as dualistic entities, embodying both undulatory and corpuscular traits. As quantum facets within the electromagnetic spectrum, they crucially convey light, playing a foundational role in understanding radiant phenomena. Despite lacking mass, photons traverse space at the speed of light, unraveling the intricacies of electromagnetic interactions. The wave-particle duality principle dictates their behavior, evident in interference and diffraction patterns. Photons, central to quantum theory, mediate electromagnetic undulations, influencing a spectrum of wavelengths. From Planck's quantization of energy to Einstein's insights, photons leave an indelible mark, impacting fields like optics, medical imaging, and quantum computation. Their exploration persists, shaping our understanding of the quantum cosmos.

We know,

$$E = h\nu = hc / \lambda \quad (1)$$

We notice that as λ approaches to lp (Planck's length), photons get the maximum frequency in this universe. According to $\nu = c / \lambda$, we can express this as $\nu_{\max} = c / lp$. For the smallest wavelength, a photon will have the highest frequency. Moreover, the wavelength can't be smaller than Planck's length. Let's find out the highest frequency of photon. So,

$$\nu_{\max} = c / lp = 1.856 \times 10^{43} \text{ Hz (Theoretical)}$$

Furthermore, the energy of an Ideal photon goes as,

$$E_{\text{Ideal photon}} = h\nu_{\max} = 12,300,742,550.64 \text{ J} = 1.23 \times 10^{10} \text{ J (Theoretical)} \quad (2)$$

The momentum of an Ideal photon goes as,

$$P_{\text{Ideal photon}} = h / lp = 41.0024 \text{ Kg m/s (Theoretical)}$$

Hence, from 1 mole Ideal photons we obtain,

$$U = 6.023 \times 10^{23} \times 12,300,742,550.64 = 7.4 \times 10^{33} \text{ J (Theoretical)}$$

Ultimately, we obtained the definition of Ideal photon.

Ideal photon: The photon whose wavelength is equal to the smallest length in the universe, or the photon with the highest frequency in the universe, is referred to as the Ideal photon.

In accordance with current quantum physics, it is entirely theoretical. If we were to discover a photon in real-life exhibiting a frequency greater than ν_{max} and possessing more energy than an ideal photon, it would affirm that the wavelength of such a photon is smaller than the Planck's length. Moreover, this discovery would substantiate that Planck's length is not the ultimate minimum length in our universe. Since it no longer holds this distinction, the equations that are built upon the assumption of Planck's length being the smallest will become invalid, leading to chaos within the realm of physics. Consequently, we would need to revise and reconstruct the fundamental theories of physics from their very foundations.

Fig:1 (Energy vs Wavelength)

MD. Shaikhul Hadis Nazat

Moulana Bhasani College, Sirajganj, Bangladesh

mdshaikhulhadisnizat@gmail.com

0000-0003-0339-022X